

POLICY BRIEF COMMON TEMPLATE

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT TITLE AND PROJECT OBJECTIVES

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02

(Developing and consolidating the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2021))

TOPIC: [Advancing responsible research assessment with open, community-governed infrastructures](#)

PROJECT: On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure (OPERAS-PLUS)

<https://operas-eu.org>

PROJECT: objectives

The general objective of the OPERAS-PLUS project is to provide the necessary support OPERAS needs to complete its preparatory phase and to transition its status into an ERIC.

This general objective is divided in several specific objectives (SOs), defined by the topic description, the recommendations provided by the ESFRI report and the issues raised by the OPERAS General Assembly in 2021:

(SO1) To develop and strengthen OPERAS governance structure, esp. financial, legal, and human resource management aspects of the infrastructure central hub in a sustainable way, compliant with RI management best practices.

(SO2) To support the establishment and development of OPERAS national nodes, set up and manage their relations with the central hub.

(SO3) To develop OPERAS portfolio of services by providing both required technology and a monitoring system for services development.

(SO4) To maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and at international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure.

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POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research assessment is undergoing a major transformation¹, driven by initiatives such as [DORA](#) and [CoARA](#), which call for more responsible, transparent, and inclusive evaluation practices. Central to this reform is the need to move beyond narrow metrics like the Journal Impact Factor and h-index, which often fail to reflect the diversity and societal value of research, especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)². Despite progress, current research assessment systems remain heavily reliant on metrics that undervalue the diverse outputs of SSH research, such as monographs, multilingual publications, and policy engagement. These challenges are both cultural and structural, rooted in a system that prioritises quantity over quality and prestige over societal

¹ Denis, M., Eweis, D. S., & Elliott, T. (2023). The future of research evaluation.

<https://doi.org/10.24948/2023.07>

² Ochsner, M., Hug, S. E., & Galleron, I. (2017). The future of research assessment in the humanities: bottom-up assessment procedures. Palgrave Communications, 3(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1057/palcomms.2017.20>

relevance. Addressing them requires not only new approaches to research assessment but a shift in what we prioritise in research evaluation, and how we can utilise open infrastructure support in this process. OPERAS places a strong emphasis on community engagement in the co-design of infrastructures and services. Its approach prioritises participation from underrepresented disciplines and regions and encourages mutual learning, aligning with the bottom-up principles promoted by CoARA. Through open, community-led services, OPERAS supports alternative publishing models, including the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), promotes transparent peer review practices, and makes visible a broad range of research outputs relevant to SSH. Its CoARA Action Plan outlines directions for aligning its services with CoARA commitments. As such, OPERAS is in a strong position to continue engaging with the SSH domain and promote research assessment reform. Below, we identify certain areas where OPERAS has been contributing and we produce four recommendations in relation to the topic of Research Assessment

- **Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities.** OPERAS Research Infrastructure actively contributes to **Priority 3 of the [ERA Policy Agenda \(2022-2024\)](#)**, supporting the reform of research assessment systems for researchers, institutions, and research itself. This aligns with OPERAS' broader vision of fostering a more open, inclusive, and sustainable research culture, particularly in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). OPERAS sees assessment reform as essential for enabling Open Science and ensuring the long-term relevance of open scholarly infrastructures. Its work is closely aligned with recent **Council Conclusions** on [research assessment](#) and on [equitable, trustworthy scholarly publishing](#), both of which validate OPERAS' approach to promoting transparency and diversity in research evaluation. OPERAS, as a **member and signatory of CoARA**, actively participates in three working groups on peer review recognition, multilingualism, and SSH evaluation. A key outcome of this engagement is the publication of the [OPERAS CoARA Action Plan](#), outlining concrete institutional commitments and a roadmap for SSH-specific reform.
 - **International co-operation of research infrastructures.** OPERAS addresses **the open access of data** through its role in the **GraspOS project**, which co-develops an open, inclusive infrastructure for research assessment rooted in Open Science. OPERAS contributes to interoperable tools and services that facilitate global access to open data and metadata, especially benefiting communities underrepresented in mainstream scholarly systems. Its [endorsement of the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) reinforces this commitment by promoting aligned metadata standards that reduce barriers to cross-border collaboration and establishing alternative evaluation infrastructures based on openness and transparency. Beyond GraspOS, on projects like GRAPHIA to further enhance the Infrastructure SSH landscape. GRAPHIA holds great potential for open research assessment efforts, through the delivery of a Knowledge Graph (KG) specifically for SSH knowledge.
 - **Level of connection of your RI to EOSC.** OPERAS Research Infrastructure maintains a strong connection to EOSC through active participation in Expert Groups such as **OA5** (Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upscaling) and **OA6** (Open Scholarly Communication). These contributions support the integration of capacity building, inclusive recognition practices, and the development of quality assessment procedures for diverse research outputs, particularly relevant to the SSH. Through its involvement in projects like [ATRIUM](#), [Skills4EOSC](#) and [GraspOS](#), OPERAS helps ensure that SSH-specific services and metadata become more FAIR-aligned and accessible via various EOSC access points. While OPERAS does not directly manage datasets, it enhances discoverability and interoperability of research outputs through open, multilingual infrastructures, such as [Gotriple.eu](#)
 - **Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation.** OPERAS Research Infrastructure drives digital innovation with a clear focus on the values shaping research assessment reform: **transparency, inclusivity, openness**, and the **recognition of diverse research contributions**. Its services are designed not only to improve scholarly communication but also to enable more equitable and meaningful evaluation practices—especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities. Through **PRISM**, OPERAS
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brings transparency to peer review by making quality assurance processes for monographs visible in a standardised way. **GoTriple** and **MONDAECUS** foster inclusivity by supporting multilingual discovery and collaborative translation, expanding the visibility of research across languages and regions. **OPERAS Metrics** offers an alternative lens for assessment of Open Access Books, providing usage and impact data tailored to SSH, where traditional citation metrics often fall short. All of these tools are developed within open, FAIR-aligned infrastructures and shaped through community input. This approach ensures that OPERAS services not only reflect reform values but also contribute actively to building a research assessment ecosystem that is open, participatory, and fit for diverse scholarly practices. A unique effort developed as part of OPERAS Research Infrastructure is the Innovation Lab, which brings together the human element, to drive innovation in many topics, including Research Assessment.

- **Funding of research infrastructures.** Research Assessment requires services and data to be developed in ways that are open, interoperable and transparent, to really create the environment CoARA, DORA, and Barcelona Declaration require. OPERAS is actively exploring funding opportunities for the development of its services in policy-relevant areas such as research assessment reform (Priority Area 3 of the ERA Policy Agenda) and Open Science implementation. By aligning its services, such as OPERAS Metrics, PRISM, and GoTriple, with broader EU priorities, OPERAS increases their relevance and eligibility for funding across thematic programmes, including Horizon Europe, EOSC, and national research strategies. OPERAS also contributes to the broader conversation on funding models by participating in discussions around the value of open, community-led infrastructures, especially in disciplines like SSH, where commercial publishing models have proven inadequate or exclusionary.
- **Sustainability of research infrastructures.** OPERAS supports the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures by developing open, community-governed services aligned with policy priorities such as research assessment reform and Open Science. Its approach to sustainability goes beyond financial stability, emphasising active community engagement and uptake. Through co-design, open governance, and ongoing collaboration with stakeholders, OPERAS ensures its services remain relevant and widely used. A self-assessment against the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI) confirmed strong alignment in openness, community participation, and financial transparency. These principles are embedded in daily operations, guiding OPERAS' strategy for lasting viability and community trust.

Key Recommendations:

1. To strengthen synergies between research assessment reform, open infrastructures, and funding frameworks, and advance the CoARA Commitments, it is essential to support the use of open information embedded in open infrastructures, while promoting more Open Science-aligned approaches. This includes the continued integration of qualitative tools such as Narrative CVs, expert peer review and [Open Science indicators](#) into EU-level evaluation mechanisms.
 2. To further strengthen this collaboration, OPERAS recommends increased representation of SSH in the EOSC federation, support for multilingual FAIR practices, and recognition of diverse scholarly outputs.
 3. Continue EU-level funding for SSH infrastructures beyond project-based development to cover the long-term operational costs of open, community-led services that advance policy goals such as research assessment reform, multilingualism, and equitable access. A mixed funding model combining institutional co-financing, national contributions, and targeted EU investment would enhance financial resilience while ensuring sustained access, visibility, and uptake within national research ecosystems. Policies should formally recognise the essential role of these infrastructures in enabling systemic reform.
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4. Maintain research assessment reform as a key priority in the European Research Area and embed it in future ERA Policy Agendas and related implementation mechanisms. Support open, community-led infrastructures as trusted spaces such as innovation labs and research infrastructure sandboxes for testing, refining, and scaling new assessment practices in close collaboration with the research community, ensuring their integration into national and European research systems.
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